

Appendix 4. Teacher's interview guide

This guide is divided in three main parts: first impressions, Achieving lesson objectives, Intended and unintended outcomes, adaptations to the lesson delivery and questions covering the factors affecting delivery and scale up of the intervention.

Instructions for interviewer (moderator)

- Review the lesson plan before the interview
- Share the interview objectives. Remind them that we are exploring the how they have achieved teaching the lessons, effects of the lessons, and factors that might have affected teaching the lessons.
- Clarify that the purpose of the interview is to evaluate the lessons and the resources, NOT to evaluate the teacher. There are no wrong or right answers.
- Remind them that their answers will be kept confidential, and they should not hesitate to be open about their experience teaching the lessons, whether positive or negative.

Instructions for Notetaker

- Make the recorder ready for discussions
- The teacher may refer to any lesson. Notetakers should be diligent about noting which lesson(s) the teacher is referring to, whenever relevant.

User test materials:

- Interview Guide
- Notebooks
- Pens/pencils
- Identification card (mandatory- if visiting study participant for the first time)
- Covid-19 PPE (masks, sanitizer, etc.)
- Voice recorder/camera

Interview session details

Date:	
School:	
School type:	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Private <input type="checkbox"/> Government-aided 1. <input type="checkbox"/> Low performing <input type="checkbox"/> High performing
Facilitator/moderator	
Observer/note taker(s)	

Teacher details (Refer to the teacher details for received)

Teachers study ID	
Teaches which subjects	
Teacher's age and sex	Sex: _____ Age (years): _____
Type of technology teacher used	<input type="checkbox"/> laptop <input type="checkbox"/> smart phone <input type="checkbox"/> pad <input type="checkbox"/> projector

Section A. TEACHER FACTORS

Question	Observer notes	Barriers and facilitators framework
<p>A1. Having been one of the teachers that participated in teaching the “Be smart about your health” lessons at your school, what are your general thoughts about the lessons?</p>		<p>Begin with an open question (also listen especially for new themes that aren’t covered below)</p>
<p>A2. The content in the “Be smart about your health” resources” might have initially felt new and unfamiliar to many teachers. How did the content feel to you?</p> <p>Probe:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If the content felt new and unfamiliar, why? - For the new elements in the content, were they hard to convey to students? 		<p>To put teacher at ease</p> <p>“Remember, we are not evaluating you. Please don’t hesitate to be open about how you felt. It is important to understand how you and other teachers perceived your own understanding of the material.”</p>
<p>A3. What sort of skills or competencies do you feel helped you teach this content in an effective way?</p> <p>Probe:</p> <p>How did those skills help to teach the content?</p> <p>What skills or competencies did you feel you lacked?</p>		<p>TEACHER</p> <p>Skills and competencies.</p>

<p>A4. What are your thoughts on the training you received in the delivery of the lessons?</p> <p>Probe: What was useful</p> <p>What was less useful or not useful</p> <p>What can be improved?</p> <p>Suggestions</p>		<p>TEACHER</p> <p>Sufficient training</p>
<p>A5. Tell me a bit about how you <u>felt</u> teaching this material to your class.</p> <p>Prompt! Name any feelings you had or have now.</p>		<p>TEACHER</p> <p>Emotions</p>
<p>A6. Did you feel <u>confident</u> about teaching these lessons?</p> <p>Example: Can you give me an example of a situation when you felt confident?</p> <p>Probe:</p> <p>What aspects of the lesson did you feel less confident or unsure to teach</p>		<p>TEACHER</p> <p>Self-efficacy</p>

<p>A7. How motivated did you feel to teach these lessons to your class – very motivated or not so motivated?</p> <p>Explanation: Can you tell me a bit about why?</p> <p>Prompt: Did you look forward to teaching these lessons? Or did you feel they were a burden somehow? (Please be honest with us!)</p>		<p>TEACHER Motivation</p>
<p>A8. Did you experience any strong differences between the lesson content and your own beliefs about treatments, or about what children or others should be encouraged to do?</p> <p>Example: Can you give an example of content that was different from your beliefs?</p> <p>Probe:</p> <p>How did these differences impact on your teaching</p>		<p>TEACHER Beliefs, attitudes</p>
<p>A9. Did you feel that you managed to engage the students during the lessons and get them thinking and discussing - or was this difficult to do with these lessons?</p> <p>Probe:</p> <p>What helped to engage students and / or what made it difficult to engage students.</p>		<p>TEACHER Positive learning environment</p>

Section B. FEEDBACK ON THE BE SMART ABOUT YOUR HEALTH SECONDARY SCHOOL RESOURCES

Question(s)	Observer notes	Barriers and facilitators framework
<p>B1. How was teaching the “Be smart about your health” lessons similar to how you teach other lessons?</p> <p>How was teaching these lessons different from how you teach other lessons?</p>		<p>TEACHER</p> <p>Fit to teacher’s teaching style and context</p>
<p>B2. Could you give an example of how you typically prepared a lesson?</p> <p>(Recall a specific lesson and explain how you went about it in detail.)</p>		<p>Fidelity evaluation</p>
<p>B3. How did you typically deliver the lessons in relation to how it was planned?</p> <p>- What helped you deliver the lessons as planned?</p> <p>- What made it difficult to deliver the lessons as planned?</p> <p>- Were there specific parts of the lessons that you could not implement in the classroom, or that were difficult to implement? If so, why?</p>		<p>Fidelity evaluation</p>

<p>- What might help teachers deliver these lessons as planned?</p>		
<p>B4. Do you think that the “Be smart about your health” resources are <u>appropriate</u> for students in your class?’. To the extent appropriate: What made them appropriate? To the extent not appropriate: What do you think should be changed to make them more appropriate?</p>		<p>TEACHING MATERIALS Appropriateness of material</p>
<p>B5. To what extent did you trust the content in the CHOICE materials: To the extent trustworthy: What made the materials trustworthy? To the extent untrustworthy: What made them untrustworthy?</p>		<p>TEACHING MATERIALS Credibility of material</p>

<p>B6. How valuable were the “Be smart about your health” resources for you as a teacher to use in your class and your school?</p> <p>To the extent valuable: What made the materials valuable?</p> <p>To the extent unvaluable: What made them unvaluable?</p>		<p>TEACHING MATERIALS</p> <p>Value of material</p>
<p>B7. Do you think these resources should be a part of the curriculum for this age group in your school?</p> <p>Do you have any thoughts about where they might fit or how they would need to be adapted to fit?</p>		
<p>B8. Taking into consideration your experience in teaching these lessons at your school, what should be in place to enable more schools like yours to introduce the “Be smart about your health” lessons into their schools?</p>		<p>Scale up</p>

Section C. FEEDBACK REGARDING STUDENTS

Question(s)	Observer notes	Barriers and facilitators framework
<p>C1. Can you tell us briefly how the students in your class responded to being taught these lessons?</p> <p>Prompt: Either positively or negatively.</p> <p>Can you give us examples of anything you remember in particular?</p>		Open question
<p>C2. Which kinds of students benefitted most from the “Be smart about your health”</p> <p>Prompt: high, average, and low performers?</p>		STUDENTS Differentiated instruction
<p>C3. How motivated were the student in your class to learn the lessons?</p> <p>To the extent motivated: What seemed to motivate them most?</p> <p>To the extent unmotivated: Why do you think they were unmotivated?</p>		STUDENTS Motivation to learn new materials
<p>C4. Do you think students were able to read and understand the “Be smart about your health” resources</p> <p>Probe: What was hard for them What was easy for them</p>		Students ability to read and understand the material.

<p>C5. Could you describe how students attended “Be smart about your health” lessons</p> <p>Probe:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reasons for attending less frequent/more frequent - Attendance of “Be smart about your health” lessons compared to other lessons at school 		<p>Pupils’ attendance or reasons for poor attendance (eg, long distance to school or inability to pay school fees).</p>
<p>C6. Could you describe the students attitudes when learning the resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attitudes towards learning, towards authorities, towards science, towards critical thinking 		<p>Pupils’ attitudes towards learning, towards authorities, towards science, towards critical thinking</p>
<p>C7. To what extent students believed the content of the “Be smart about your health”</p>		<p>Pupils’ beliefs about the content</p>
<p>C8. In your opinion, how did home environment affect learning the “Be smart about your health”</p>		<p>The extent to which the pupil’s home environment encourages or discourages learning from the lessons.</p>
<p>C9. How did other students (peers) affect learning the “Be smart about your health” lessons.</p>		<p>Positive or negative attitudes of other pupils towards the material.</p>

Section D. School system and environment

Question(s)	Observer notes	Barriers and facilitators framework
<p>D1. How <u>easy or difficult</u> was it for you to take on and to teach the “Be smart about your health” lessons in addition to all your other responsibilities at the school?</p> <p>Prompt: Did you have sufficient resources to carry out the teaching effectively? Did you have sufficient time in your schedule? Were these lessons competing for time that you feel might have been spent better doing other things? Was it a burden to prepare for lessons?</p>		<p>SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT</p> <p>Time constraints</p> <p>Competing priorities</p> <p>School resources</p> <p>Competing</p>
<p>D2. Besides time constraints, were there <u>other factors that made it difficult</u> to teach these lessons in your school, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of support/interest from your leaders • lack of support/interest from your peers • lack of support/interest from parents or community • School resources (human, equipment, etc) • Political environment • Bureaucracy • Incentives and disincentives 		<p>SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT</p>

Section E. Intended effects, unintended effect and transfer

Question(s)	Observer notes	Adverse effect and transfer
<p style="color: red;">E1. Have you experienced or observed the lessons having <u>any advantages</u> to students? If so, please tell us about it.</p> <p>Probe</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assertiveness (students asking more questions and not taking things for granted) • Improved decision---making (<i>students making more thoughtful and informed decisions</i>) <p>Creativity (<i>Thinking outside the box</i>)</p>		intended effects
<p style="color: red;">E2. Have you experienced or observed the lessons having <u>any disadvantages</u> to students? If so, please tell us about it.</p> <p>Prompt:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Misunderstanding • Conflict (students and teachers, parents, or other authorities) • Distraction • Stress, or other uncomfortable thoughts or feeling • Wasted time or resources 		unintended effects

<p>E3. Have your students <u>used anything they learned in the lessons at home with family/ when they are with friends? If so, please tell us about it.</u></p> <p>Prompt:</p> <p>-Have they <u>taken something learned in the lessons and used it in a different subject or field?</u></p>		Transfer of learning
<p>E6. Do you have any suggestions of other possible good or bad impacts that “Be smart about your health” resources or learning these concepts might have on people?</p>		Intended and unintended effects

Section F. Other

<p>F1. Do you have <u>any other feedback</u> you'd like to share with us, either positive or negative about these resources or your involvement in this project?</p>		Open question
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Section G. Feedback on our session.

Question(s)	Observer notes	Barriers and facilitators framework
<p>G1. How has this <u>interview</u> been conducted? Prompt! What can we make better?</p>		

Section H. Immediate discussion after the session

Observer notes